

PHYCONANOTECHNOLOGY: SYNTHESIS OF GOLD NANOPARTICLES USING SEAWEEDS - UV- VISIBLE SPECTROSCOPY AND FTIR STUDIES

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ABSTRACT

*Nanotechnology has emerged as a transformative field with broad applications across diverse scientific domains. Among its many innovations, the biosynthesis of nanoparticles—particularly gold nanoparticles (AuNPs)—has garnered significant attention due to its eco-friendly, cost-effective, and biocompatible characteristics. In this study, the green synthesis of gold nanoparticles was achieved using two marine macroalgae species, *Sargassum wightii* and *Gracilaria corticata*. These seaweeds are rich in bioactive compounds such as proteins, flavonoids, and phenolics, which serve dual roles as reducing and capping agents during nanoparticle formation. The resulting nanoparticles were characterized by their stability, size distribution, and surface morphology, underscoring the potential of marine algae as sustainable biological resources for nanoparticle synthesis. This method presents a viable alternative to traditional chemical routes, offering promising implications for applications in biomedicine, environmental remediation, and nanotechnology.*

Keywords: Au-nanoparticles, H₂AuCl₄, Seaweed-nanobiotechnology, Metal solutions, Biosynthesis.

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1. Introduction

In various fields of science and technology, the immensely emerging field nanotechnology results in a wide range of applications. The word “nano” means dwarf or extremely small, is derived from a Greek word (Rai *et al.*, 2008). Nanoparticle (10⁻⁹m) is a small object which acts as a whole unit in terms of its transport and properties. The application of nanotechnology is emerged in various fields like optics, electronics, catalysis, biomedicine, magnetic, mechanics, energy science, biotechnology, physics, chemistry, material science etc. (Rai *et al.*, 2008 and Huang *et al.*, 2007). Phyco-nano-synthesis of gold nanoparticles has substantial attention in modern applied science and technology. The increased utilization of nanoparticle is due to its unique property as it is cost effective over physic-chemical method and as it avoids the toxic risk (Mehrdad and Khalil 2010). Enormous benefits, compatibility for pharmaceutical and other biomedical applications and to environment is possible due to the synthesis of gold nanoparticles using ecofriendly materials like algae, fungi, bacteria and plant extracts (Parashar *et al.*, 2009 and Saifuddin *et al.*, 2009).

Seaweeds, the marine macroalgae grows in the sea or on rocks below the high-water mark. The biomolecules present in seaweeds such as proteins, flavonoids and phenols not only play a role in reducing the ions to nano size but also plays an effective role in capping of the nanoparticles (Shankar *et al.*, 2004). The present study is focused on the synthesis of gold nanoparticles using two marine algae *Sargassum wightii* (Greville) and *Gracilaria corticata* (J. Agardh) before and after phycoremediation.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Collection of algae and extract preparation

The seaweed samples, *Gracilara corticata* and *Sargassum wightii* was collected from the Kovalam coast, near Chennai and Mandapam coast, Gulf of Mannar region Rameshwaram.

2.2 Biosynthesis of gold nanoparticles

The algae was washed and dried in an oven at 60°C, ground with an agate mortar, and sieved to a mesh size of <0.5 mm. Before experimentation, the biomass was washed thrice in deionized water to remove the unwanted materials. For the synthesis of gold nanoparticles, chloroauric acid (HAuCl_4^-) (Sd fine) was used. Double-distilled deionized water was used for all the experiments. Gold nanoparticles formations were carried out by taking 500 mg of dry biomass in a 250 ml Erlenmeyer flask with 10^{-3} M aqueous HAuCl_4^- solution and incubated at room temperature. The pH was checked during the course of reaction and it was found to be 5.09.

1. Metal solutions

Gold reduction studies were carried out with fresh solutions that were prepared from a 1000 mg/l stock solution of hydrochloroauric acid (HAuCl_4^-). The initial pH values were adjusted with NaOH flakes and Hcl as needed.

The present study includes time dependent formation of gold nanoparticles employing UV-Visible spectrophotometer, size and morphology by employing: TEM, structure from powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) technique and understanding of cell wall polysaccharide-gold nanoparticles interaction from Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) spectroscopy.

2. UV- Visible spectroscopy

(Jorgensen, 1962; Mie, 1908; Faraday, 1857; Papavassiliou, 1980; Link and Sayed, 1999)

3. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (Banwell and Mc Cash, 1996)

3. Results

3.1 Biosynthesis and characterization of gold nanoparticles using the experimental algae

Nanoparticles of noble metals are characterized by the presence of bright colours ascribed to the oscillations of the surface electron cloud of these particles. The collective oscillations of electrons of a nanoparticle upon interaction with light of suitable energy causes

the nanoparticles to attain colour specific to particular metal. The frequency of oscillation is strongly dependent on the particle size, shape and aggregation.

The present study is focused on the biosynthesis and characterization of gold nanoparticles using the experimental algae.

A. UV-Visible spectrum of gold nanoparticles of the experimental algae

Reduction of the aqueous chloroaurate ion during the exposure to the biomass of experimental algae may be easily followed by UV-Visible spectroscopy. It is well known that gold nanoparticles exhibit lovely pink- ruby red colour, these colour arise due to the excitation of surface plasmon vibrations in the gold nanoparticles as shown in (Plate I). After 2 hr of aging in the first reaction the colour changed from pale yellow to ruby red, where concentration of HAuCl_4^- was 10^{-3} M. The gold nanoparticles of surface plasmon band occurs in the range 510-560 nm in an aqueous medium. In the *Sargassum sp* is observed that the wavelength of the gold surface plasmon resonance band occurs initially and stabilized at ca.550 nm after 2 hr of reaction as shown in (Fig. 1). While in *Gracilaria sp* shows absorption at ca 530 nm after 2 hr of reaction as shown in (Fig. 2).

Plate I: Picture showing the filtrate of the experimental algal biomass in aqueous solution of 1×10^{-3} M at the beginning of reaction (a) and after 2hr of reaction (b)

A. *Sargassum sp*, B. *Gracilaria sp*

Fig. 1: UV -visible range spectrum of gold nanoparticles showing the surface Plasmon band of the *Sargassum sp*.

Fig. 2: UV -visible range spectrum of gold nanoparticles showing the surface Plasmon band of the *Gracilaria sp.*

B. FT-IR spectrum of gold nanoparticles synthesized of the experimental algae

Figure 4 shows the FT-IR spectrum recorded from the Chlorauric acid solution after reaction with *Sargassum sp* for 2 hr. The presence of six bands 3464.81, 2928.23, 1739.06, 1375.12, 1244.27 and 1048.21 cm^{-1} is seen in the figure 4. The 3464.81 cm^{-1} band may be assigned to carboxylic acids (O-H), the 2928.23 cm^{-1} band may be assigned to alkanes (C-H) stretching vibrations. The 1739.06 cm^{-1} band may be assigned to primary amines, N-H bend (C, O) stretching vibrations, the 1375.12 cm^{-1} band may be assigned to N=O stretching vibrations, the 1244.27 cm^{-1} band may be assigned to C-O stretching vibrations and 1048.21 cm^{-1} band may be assigned C-N stretching vibrations in the amide linkages of the proteins (Table.1). The increase in the intensity of the bands at 1375.12 cm^{-1} suggests the presence of other types of binding sites for Au.

Fig. 3: FT-IR spectrum of the gold nanoparticles synthesized of *Sargassum sp*

Table 1: FT-IR spectral assignments of gold nanoparticles of *Sargassum*

Group	Frequency Range (cm ⁻¹)
Carboxylic acids (O-H)	3464.81
Alkanes (C-H stretch)	2928.23
N-H bend (C, O stretch)	1739.06
N=O	1375.12
C-O stretch	1244.27
C-N stretch	1048.21

The FT-IR spectrum recorded from gold nanoparticles synthesized using *Gracilaria sp* biomass. A number of broad bands are observed in the region 1120.21, 1276.51, 1602.59, 2928.63 and 3435.98 cm⁻¹ (Fig. 4) were observed. The 1120.21cm⁻¹ band may be assigned C-N stretching vibrations in the amide linkage of the proteins, the 1276.51cm⁻¹ band may be assigned Ether (Aromatic) vibrations, the 1602.59cm⁻¹ band may be assigned N-H bend (C, O)

stretching vibration and the band 2928.63cm^{-1} band may be assigned to alkanes (C-H) stretching vibrations and the band 3435.98cm^{-1} may be assigned to carboxylic acids (O-H) (Table.2).

Fig. 4: FT-IR spectrum of the gold nanoparticles synthesized of *Gracilaria sp*

Table 2: FT-IR spectrum of assignments gold nanoparticles of *Gracilaria sp*

<i>Group</i>	Frequency Range (cm^{-1})
Carboxylic acids (O-H)	3435.98
Alkanes (C-H)	2928.63
C=C Stretch	1602.59
Ether (Aromatic)	1276.51
C-N stretch	1120.21

4. Discussion

4.1 Phyconanotechnology

The seaweeds were successfully recovered and reduced Au (III) to Au (O). In the process, gold nanoparticles were formed. Gold reduction with experimental algae is effective, nutrient independent, did not use toxic chemicals at neutral pH values. This could be an alternative process for gold recovering from dilute hydrometallurgical solutions and for the synthesis of reduced gold nanoparticles. An important potential benefit of the described method of synthesis of nanoparticles using marine algae is that they are quite stable in solution and this is a very important advantage over other biological methods currently in use. The release of gold nanoparticles of *S.wightii* of control were higher compared to oil effluent treated *S.wightii*. While the release of gold nanoparticles of oil treated *G.corticata* was higher compared to *G.corticata* (control). The biomass had a pale yellow colour before reaction with the gold ions, which changed to dark purple on completion of the reaction. The appearance of the purple colour clearly indicated the formation of gold nanoparticles in the reaction mixture. The characteristic pink-purple colour of 139 colloidal gold solutions is due to excitation of surface plasmon vibrations in the nanoparticles and provides a convenient spectroscopic signature of their formation. The researchers reported that upon filtration, the biomass was still pale yellow but that the aqueous solution contained the gold nanoparticles. This indicates that the reduction of the AuCl₄⁻ ions takes place intracellularly. The researchers suggested that most probably, the reduction of the AuCl₄⁻ ions occurs due to reductases released by the alga into solution. Extra cellular reduction of gold using higher plants such as *Pelargonium graveolens* [Geranium] (Shankar et al., 2003) and *Avena sativa* [Oat] (Armendariz et al., 2004) have indicated that the extracellular biogenesis of gold nano particles was carried out by non-viable biomass only. There are several physical and chemical methods for the synthesis of metallic nanoparticles that are followed by the material scientists (Edelstein and Cammarata, 1996). Nanotechnology requires the collaboration between physicists, chemists, biologists and engineers since microbes have shown ability to reduce metal ions to form nanoparticles. As shown in this study, the gold nanoparticles were synthesized in the extra-cellular cell supernatant of alga. This offers a great advantage over an intra-cellular process of synthesis from the application point of view. Since the nanoparticles formed inside the algae would require additional step of processing for the release of the nanoparticles from the algae by ultra sound treatment or by reaction with suitable detergents. Using metal-accumulating microorganisms as a tool for the production of nanoparticles and their assembly for the

construction of new advanced materials, is a completely new technological approach. The plasmon resonance for gold nanoparticles in aqueous solution appeared at approximately 530 nm and changed according to the size of the nanoparticles (Sarma and Chattopadhyay, 2004). Novel properties derived from unusually shaped nanoparticles can be generally exhibited through plasmon absorption spectroscopy because their optical properties of aqueous suspensions intimately associate with the shape (Zhang et al., 2004) compared with the spherical nanoparticles, the UV-Visible absorption of uniquely shaped gold nanoparticles usually shows the red-shift and wider peak (Zhanget al., 2004). It can be clearly seen that the more irregular nanoparticles 140 possess the more red-shifts and wider absorption peaks, indicating that the UV-Visible absorption property of colloidal solution intimately depends on its shape. These broad and multiple absorption peaks should probably result from the variable dimensions along to multiple axes of these particles (Orendorff, 2005). Lin et al., (2005) observed modifications of these bands after gold recovery with *S. cerevisiae*. Which may be due to hydrolysis of such groups caused a decrease in the amount of gold recovered. Gamez et al., (2000) observed a decrease of the gold recovery when the carboxyl groups were esterified. Nevertheless, the displacement of these bands was not apparent in our study. The displacement of the asymmetric vibrations of the carboxyl groups ($1650.77\text{--}2090.47\text{cm}^{-1}$) was only slightly above the resolution of the spectrophotometer (4 cm^{-1}). Other functional groups have also been associated to gold recovery, but no reduction has been reported. Figueira et al., (1999), using FT-IR and XPS, mention that acetyl groups could also be involved in metal sorption of trivalent metals with brown algae.

5. Conclusion

A preliminary study of phyconanotechnology using gold nano particles showed that the amount of gold nanoparticles produced by *S. wightii* were high in control than in treated while the tolerant *G. corticata* produced more nanoparticles in the hydrocarbon remediated compared to that of control.

Wastewater treatment is one area where nanotechnology can take active part. This technique is advantageous over traditional technologies such as quick oxidation, no formation of polycyclic products and oxidation of pollutants. Thus, it is an effective and rapid technique for the removal of hydrocarbons.

The formation of peak at (111) X-ray diffraction pattern confirmed the synthesis of gold nanoparticles was possible using both the seaweeds. The results revealed that *Sargassum wightii*. effective in synthesis. The nanoparticle synthesized was found to have a size of 6.31nm. Future studies could be focused on the applications of synthesized gold nanoparticles.

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